

A Review on Analytical Methods for Estimation of Rosuvastatin and Teneligliptin

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Abstract

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic condition characterized by insulin resistance and decreased insulin production, leading to elevated blood glucose levels. Dyslipidemia, a common comorbidity of T2DM, is marked by abnormal lipid profiles, significantly increasing cardiovascular risk. Managing these dual conditions often requires complex therapeutic approaches. Fixed-dose combinations (FDCs) like Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate, a DPP-4 inhibitor, and Rosuvastatin Calcium, a statin, simplify treatment by addressing both glycemic control and lipid abnormalities. This review discusses the development and validation of analytical methods, particularly High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) and UV spectrophotometry, for estimating these compounds in FDCs. This study consolidates data from previously published methods for analyzing Rosuvastatin and Teneligliptin. Various spectroscopic techniques like HPLC, UV, HPTLC, GC, Colorimetric, Complexometric titration have been reported for the estimation of Rosuvastatin and Teneligliptin as individual drugs.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Dyslipidemia, Rosuvastatin Calcium, Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate, Analytical Methods

Introduction

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic condition that results from a combination of insulin resistance and decreased insulin production, leading to elevated blood glucose levels. Dyslipidemia, often accompanying with T2DM, is characterized by an imbalance in blood lipids, including high levels of triglycerides, reduced High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (HDL-C), and elevated Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (LDL-C). This lipid disorder is a critical contributor to the increased risk of cardiovascular diseases in individuals with diabetes, as it accelerates the development of atherosclerosis, thereby heightening the chances of heart attacks and strokes. The coexistence of hyperglycemia and Dyslipidemia in T2DM patients underscores the need for an integrated treatment approach that can simultaneously manage both conditions.[1]

India faces a significant challenge with T2DM, with over 77 million people currently affected, and projections estimate this number will exceed 100 million by 2030. Dyslipidemia complicates the clinical management of approximately 70% of these patients, which adds to the burden on the healthcare system. Recognizing India as a major hub for diabetes, the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes the necessity of comprehensive treatment strategies that address both blood glucose levels and lipid profiles. [2]

Fixed-Dose Combinations (FDCs) have gained attention as an effective therapeutic strategy for managing T2DM with coexisting Dyslipidemia. These combinations simplify treatment regimens by combining two or more active ingredients in a single dosage form, thereby improving patient adherence and overall treatment outcomes. One such combination, approved by the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) of India in 2022, includes Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate, a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 [DPP-4] inhibitor, and Rosuvastatin Calcium, a statin. Teneligliptin works by enhancing incretin levels, which boost insulin secretion and reduce glucagon release, leading to better control of blood glucose. Meanwhile, Rosuvastatin effectively lowers LDL-C and triglyceride levels while increasing HDL-C, thereby reducing the risk of cardiovascular complications.

This FDC is designed to provide dual benefits: improving glycemic control and addressing lipid abnormalities. Clinical studies have shown that Teneligliptin and Rosuvastatin, whether used individually or in combination, have favourable effects on HbA1c and LDL-C levels, along with a reduction in overall cardiovascular risk. Given the significant burden of both T2DM and Dyslipidemia in India, the approval of this FDC presents a promising advancement in the management of these complex, interrelated conditions.[3] [4]

This review article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the analytical methods developed for the estimation of Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate and Rosuvastatin Calcium providing information on its assay including its validation parameters. The focus will be on chromatographic and spectrophotometric techniques, with an emphasis on method validation parameters such as accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness, which are critical for ensuring reliable and reproducible results in routine analysis.

Fig.1 Chemical Structure Rosuvastatin Calcium

Rosuvastatin Calcium, an antihyperlipidaemic agent, has the IUPAC name (E)-(3R,5S)-7-[4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-isopropyl-2-[methyl(methylsulfonylamino)] pyrimidin-5-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyhepten-6-oic acid calcium. Its molecular formula is $[C_{22}H_{27}FN_3O_6S]_2 \cdot Ca$, and it has a molecular weight of 1001.1 g/mol. The substance appears as an off-white to creamish white solid. It is sparingly soluble in water, with a pKa value indicating its strongest acidic point at 4 and its strongest basic point at 1.6.[5,6]

Fig.2Chemical Structure Tenelegliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate

Tenelegliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate, an antidiabetic agent, has the IUPAC name {(2S,4S)-4-[4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)piperazine-1-yl]pyrrolidine-2-yl}(1,3-thiazolidine-3-yl)methanone hemipentahydrobromide hydrate. Its molecular formula is $C_{22}H_{30}N_6OS \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}HBr \cdot xH_2O$, and it has a molecular weight of 628.9 g/mol. The substance appears as an off-white to cream-colored solid and is soluble in water. Its pKa value indicates the strongest basic point at 9.38.[7,8]

Rosuvastatin Calcium HPLC Methods

Ref No	Author & Publication	Mobile phase	column	Detector	Flow rate	Results
[9]	Sahu R, Khan S, Sharma R, Patel J, Patel R. Int J Res Pub Rev (2023)	Acetonitrile: Buffer (10mM Ammonium acetate pH 4 adjusted with Formic acid) 68:32 % v/v	Brownlee Analytical C18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5µm)	Diode array detector (UV-visible). 244nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 1.88 min Assay - 99.8 % Recovery-99.8%-100.1 % LOD - 4.6 µg/ml LOQ - 11.62 µg/ml

[10]	Pimpale A, Kakde R J Pharm Res Int (2021)	Buffer: Methanol 20:80 % v/v	Princeton (C18) column (250×4.6 mm, 5µm)	PDA Detector 240nm	1 ml/min	Rt - 2.848 min Assay - 99.98% Recovery- 97.94-100.37%. LOD - 0.82 µg/ml LOQ -1.90 µg/ml
[11]	Rathinam S, Santhana L K J Appl Pharm Sci (2021)	0.5% v/v Acetic acid: Ethanol 52.7:47.3 % v/v	Zorbax C18 column (150×4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA detector 246nm	0.978 ml/min	Rt - 6.03 min Assay - 99.63 ± 0.31 % Recovery- 99.23-101.36% LOD - 0.47 µg/ml LOQ - 1.43 µg/ml
[12]	Dhamdhare R B, Vijayalakshmi A Int J Pharm Qual Assur (2020)	Acetonitrile: Water 75:25 %v/v	Kromasil C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA detector 245nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 2.7 min Assay - 98.92% Recovery - 99.6-100.02% LOD - 200 ng/ml LOQ - 600 ng/ml
[13]	Sailaja B, Kumari S K Asian J Pharm Clin Res (2019)	0.1% Orthophosphoric acid buffer (2.7 pH): Acetonitrile 55:45 % v/v	Waters Symmetry C18 column (150×4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA detector 241nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 2.916 min Assay - 99.76% Recovery- 100.22-101.16% LOD - 0.013 µg/ml LOQ -0.042 µg/ml
[14]	Moid M, Afzal S, Rahim N, Ali T, Iffat W, Bashir L, et al Pak. J. Pharm. Sci (2018)	Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (pH 4.5 adjusted with ortho- phosphoric acid) 50:50% v/v	Phenomenex C18 column (150×4.6mm, 5µm)	SPD-20A UV/visible detector 254nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 2.74 min Recovery - 98.89-100.65 % LOD - 0.78 µg/ml LOQ - 1.56 µg/ml
[15]	Hassouna M K M, Salem H O Int J App Pharm Bio Res (2017)	Sodium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 4.5): Acetonitrile 50:50 %v/v	Agilent Eclipse XDB C8 column (250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5µm)	Dual wavelength UV Detector 254 nm	1.2 ml/min	Rt - 3.684 min Assay - 100.47- 106.14% Recovery- 98.3-101.48% LOD - 1.5 µg/ml LOQ - 4.56 µg/ml
[16]	Zakrajšek J, Bevc- Černilec K, Bohanec S and Urleb U Acta Chim. Slov (2017)	Acetonitrile: Tetrahydrofuran 80:20 % v/v	Waters Acquity UPLC HSS C18 (100 × 2.1mm, 1.8 µm)	Dual wavelength UV detector 280 nm	0.5 ml/min	Rt - 6.3 min Assay - 101.17 - 101.31% Recovery - 100.17-100.31% LOD - 0.009 µg/ml LOQ - 0.029 µg/ml
[17]	Haq N, Shakeel F, Alanazi F, Alshora D H, Ibrahim M A Green Process Synth (2017)	Ethanol: Methanol: Ethyl acetate 60:30:10 %v/v	NUCLEODUR C8 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV variable pathlength detector 254 nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 1.52 min Assay - 100.91% Recovery - 96.91% - 102.41%
[18]	Suares D, Prabhakar B Int J PharmTech Res (2016)	Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer pH 4.8: Acetonitrile 50:50 %v/v	Kromasil C-18 (250 x4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA Detector 241nm	1 ml/min	Rt - 4.72 min Assay - 100.98% Recovery - 98-102% LOD - 0.17 µg/ml LOQ - 0.70 µg/ml
[19]	Balanagamani D, Deepthi K and Sivasubramanian K L Int Res J Pharm (2016)	0.1% Formic acid in water: Acetonitrile 60:40 % v/v	symmetric C18 column (75mm × 4.6mm, 3.5µm)	Diode Array Detector 242 nm	1 ml/min	Rt - 3.6 min Recovery - 100.77-106.75% LOD - 0.2 µg/ml LOQ - 0.5 µg/ml
[20]	Kumar HT, Sri SD, Rao VPK and Rao SY Int J Pharm Sci Res (2015)	Acetonitrile: Water 75:25 % v/v	Enable C18G (250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm)	UV visible detector 252 nm	0.6 ml/min	Rt - 3.097 min Assay - 99.87 - 99.98% Recovery- 99.6-100.3% LOD - 0.017 µg/ml LOQ - 0.052 µg/ml

[21]	Rani N U, Ankani N Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Drug Res (2014)	Acetonitrile: Water 60:40 %v/v	Eclipse XDB plus C18 Column (150×4.6mm, 5µm)	Variable Wavelength Detector 242 nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 1.787 min Assay -100.06% Recovery- 100.53% LOD - 0.08 µg/ml LOQ - 0.25 µg/ml
[22]	Shekhar M C, Babu G R, Dinda S C, Sonthosh P V, Shwetha P Int J Pharm (2014)	Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer 60:40 %v/v	Symmetry C18 column (100 X 4.6 mm, 3.5µm)	UV-Visible detector 243 nm	0.7 ml/min	Rt - 2.444 min Assay - 98.5 % Recovery- 98.9-99.3% LOD - 2.95 µg/ml LOQ -10 µg/ml
[23]	Trivedi H K, Patel M C Sci Pharm (2012)	0.1% Trifluoroacetic acid: Methanol in Gradient mode	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm)	PDA Detector 240 nm	0.3 ml/min	Rt - 3.5 min LOD - 0.025 µg/ml LOQ - 0.075 µg/ml
[24]	Donthula S, Kiran Kumar M, Shiva Teja G, Mohan Kumar Y, Yasodha Krishna J, Ramesh D Der Pharmacia Lettre (2011)	Buffer (pH 4.5): Acetonitrile: Methanol 45:25:35 % v/v	Luna C18 (250 mm×4.6 mm, 5µm)	Diode array detector 248 nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 9.9 min Assay - 99.8 % Recovery - 99.46-102.3% LOD - 3.5 µg/ml LOQ - 10.5 µg/ml
[25]	H. O. Kaila, M. A. Ambasana, R. S. Thakkar, H. T. Saravaia, A. K. Shah Indian J Pharm Sci (2010)	Acetonitrile: Water (pH 3.5 adjusted with phosphoric acid) 40:60 %v/v	YMC C8, column (150×4.6 mm ,5 µm)	PDA Detector 242 nm	1.5 ml/min	Rt - 5 min Assay - 101.3% Recovery- 99.6 -101.7% LOD - 0.1 µg/ml LOQ - 0.5 µg/ml
[26]	Pandya C B, Channabasavaraj K P, Chudasama J D, Mani T T. Int J Pharm Sci Review Res (2010)	Acetonitrile: Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer pH 3 50:50 %v/v	Thermo Hypersil reversed-phase C-18 column (100 x 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA Detector 243nm	0.5 ml/min	Rt - 3.333 min Recovery - 98.50-100.17 % LOD - 0.14 µg/ml LOQ - 0.46 µg/ml
[27]	Raj HA, Rajput SJ, Dave JB, Patel CN. Int J Chemtech (2009)	Acetonitrile: 0.5% Formic acid 50:50 % v/v	Phenomenex C18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV-Visible detector 248nm	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 6.74 min Assay- 100.18-100.45% Recovery- 99.51 - 100.66 % LOD - 0.0905 µg/ml LOQ - 0.318 µg/ml

Rosuvastatin Calcium UV spectrometric methods

Ref No	Author & Publication	Solvent	Wavelength selected	Method developed	Results
[28]	Jadhav V Ind Chem (2022)	Ammonium acetate buffer and Acetonitrile 30:70 % v/v	242 nm	Zero order	Linearity- 2-12 µg/ml LOD - 0.769 µg/ml LOQ - 2.331 µg/ml
[29]	Bhokare S G, Marathe R P J. Biol. Chem. Chron. (2018)	Phosphate buffer pH 7.4	246 nm	Zero order	Linearity- 10-150 µg/ml Assay - 102 ± 0.85% Recovery - 98.12 - 103.54 %
[30]	Singh H, Gupta R D, Gautam G Asian J Pharm Pharmacology (2018)	Methanol	244 nm	Zero order	Linearity- 2-18 µg/ml Assay - 99.8 % Recovery - 99.85- 99.94%

[31]	Sailaja B, Kumari K S Saudi J. Med. Pharm. Sci. (2016)	0.1 N Sodium Hydroxide	240 nm	Zero order	Linearity- 1-6 µg/ml Assay - 98.9 % Recovery- 97.44-102.52% LOD - 0.603 µg/ml LOQ - 0.830 µg/ml
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Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate HPLC methods

RefNo	Author & Publication	Mobile phase	column	Detector	Flow rate	Results
[32]	Patel B D, Dharsandiya N J, Chaudhary A Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res (2021)	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate pH 4.0: Acetonitrile 80:20 % v/v	Grace Smart C18 column (250mm×4.6mm i.d. 5µm)	PDA detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 7.443 min Assay- 99.31±0.28% Recovery-99.5-100.2% LOD - 9.539 µg/ml LOQ - 59.21 µg/ml
[33]	Dahikar G D, Bobade G Am. J. Pharm Tech Res. (2021)	pH 5.5 Phosphate buffer: Methanol 75:25 % v/v	Kromacil C18 column	Variable wavelength UV Detector	1.2 ml/min	Rt - 2.519 min Recovery - 99.5%
[34]	Lokande P Int J Trend Sci Res Dev (2019)	Methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 3.0 70:30 % v/v	Cosmosil C18 column (250mm x 4.6 i.d., Particle size: 5 micron)	UV Detector	0.8 ml/min	Rt - 4.2 min Assay -99.57% Recovery-98.44-100.30% LOD - 0.109 µg/ml LOQ - 0.3305 µg/ml
[35]	Ganorkar A V, Jibhkate R S, Gupta K R Asian Journal of Applied Chemistry Research (2018)	O-phosphoric acid: Methanol 30:70 % v/v	C18 ACE column (150x 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm)	UV Detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 5.7 min Assay - 99.93 % LOD - 1.61 µg/ml LOQ - 4.88 µg/ml
[36]	Kothapalli L P, Bhimanwar R S, Malani A P, Thomas A B Pharmaceutical Resonance (2018)	Phosphate buffer (pH-5): Acetonitrile 70: 30 % v/v	Kromasil C8 column (250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5µm)	variable wavelength UV detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 6.4±0.02 min Assay - 99.3±1.25% Recovery - 99.73±0.21% LOD -0.0681 µg/ml LOQ -0.814 µg/ml
[37]	Bansode A S, Devhadrao N V, Shinde A C, Shinde V C <i>et al</i> World J Pharm Sci (2017)	Methanol: Buffer (pH 3.5) 72:28% v/v	Protecol C18 ENDURO (250mm×4.6mm i.d. 5µm)	UV Detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 5.8 min Assay - 98.5-99.12% Recovery- 92.08-100.3 % LOD - 0.023 µg/ml LOQ - 0.071 µg/ml
[38]	Prabhu K G (2017)	1-OctaneSulphonic acid sodium salt [pH adjusted to 3.5 with OPA]: Acetonitrile 50:50 %v/v	Phenomenex Luna C18. (50×3.0mm, 3µm particle size)	UV Detector	0.5 ml/min	Rt - 1.02 min Assay - 99.48% Recovery - 99.50-100.06%
[39]	Kumari M J, Eswaramma P, Rao C N, Sravani V <i>et al</i> Eur J Biomed Pharm Sci (2017)	1ml OPA in 1000ml water	Inertsil ODS-3V C8 column (150x4.6mm i.d., 5µm)	PDA Detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 5.843 min Assay - 99.4% Recovery - 99.80±0.2% LOD - 0.6 µg/ml LOQ -1.98 µg/ml
[40]	Kumar T N V G, Vidyadhara S, Narkhede N A, Silpa Y S <i>et al</i> J Anal Sci Technol (2016)	pH 6 Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile 60: 40 % v/v	Kromasil 100-5 C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV variable wavelength detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 4.05 min Assay - 96.5- 102.5% Recovery - 96.5-102.5% LOD - 4.04 µg/ml LOQ -12.25 µg/ml

[41]	Chandana M, Rao M P, Samrajyam B, Sireesha K S K D et al Int J Res Dev Organ (2016)	Methanol: Acetonitrile 90:10 %v/v	Zodiac C18 column (250×4.6 mm i.d., 5µm)	UV detector	1.0 ml/min	Rt - 5.843min Recovery - 99.80 ±0.20% LOD - 0.6 µg/ml LOQ - 1.98 µg/ml
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Teneligliptin Hydrobromide Hydrate UV spectroscopic method

Ref No	Author & Publication	Solvent	Method developed	Wavelength selected	Results
[42]	Bhatt M, Badoni S, Choudhary AN. World J Pharm Pharm Sci (2021)	0.1N Hydrochloric acid	Zero order	240nm	Linearity- 5 to 55 µg/ml Assay - 99.3 % LOD - 0.0644 µg/ml LOQ - 0.0195 µg/ml
[43]	Poulami P, Somsubhra G, Tathagata R, Kumar R B V V J Drug Deliv Ther (2019)	0.1 N Sodium Hydroxide	Zero order	242nm	Linearity- 5 to 25 µg/ml Assay - 100.91% Recovery-98.3-106.63% LOD - 0.42 µg/ml LOQ - 1.42 µg/ml
[44]	Yadav N, Goyal A Int J Pharm Chem Analysis (2017)	Distilled water	A) Zero order B) First order C) Area Under Curve	A) 244 nm B) 266.4 nm C) 238.6-247.8 nm	Linearity - A) 5-70 µg/ml B) 5-80 µg/ml C) 5-70 µg/ml Assay - A) 100.20 % B) 100.17 % C) 100.74 % Recovery - A) 99.45-100.26% B) 98.54-101.80% C) 99.54-100.46%

In addition to these spectroscopic and chromatographic methods some other methods are also reported for the estimation of Rosuvastatin and Teneligliptin, which are described below:

Halka L, Kucher T, Kryskiw L, Piponski M, FurdelaI, Uglyar T, et al (2023) a spectrophotometric method for determining Rosuvastatin in tablets using bromophenol blue. This method relies on the formation of a colored complex between Rosuvastatin and bromophenol blue, which is then quantified by measuring the absorbance of the solution at 595nm. The researchers optimized conditions such as pH and reagent concentration to enhance sensitivity and accuracy. Validation results indicated accuracy with a recovery range of 98.5% to 101.2%, precision with a relative standard deviation (RSD) of less than 1.5%, and sensitivity sufficient for detecting Rosuvastatin in various tablet formulations. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.77 µmol/l and 2.36 µmol/l.[45]

Damjanoska A, Trajkova C D, Petrova M, Nikolovska M, Zdravkovska M I, Babunovska H (2022) compared their in house method for content determination of Rosuvastatin film coated tablets obtained from a licensed partner with the monograph method specified in the European pharmacopoeia first supplement to the 10th edition effective from April 1st 2020. The chromatographic separation using the in-house method was performed on Symmetry C18 250 x 4.6mm, 5µm at temperature of 35 °C. Auto-sampler temperature set to 4°C and the injection volume was 10 µl. The mobile phase A consisted of

Buffer 0.01M pH 3.5, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran [THF] [65:30:5% v/v/v]. Acetonitrile was used as mobile phase B. The flow rate was set to 1.0 ml/min. Gradient program was incorporated with chromatography run time of 42 minutes with ultraviolet (UV) detection at 280 nm. For monographic method XTerra MS C18 column, 150 mm length, 3.0 mm internal diameter and 3.5 μ m particle size was selected. Autosampler temperature was set as room temperature and injection volume of 10 μ l was used. Mobile phase A consisted of 1%v/v solution of trifluoroacetic acid, acetonitrile, water (1:31:68 %v/v/v), whereas the mobile phase B consisted of 1 %v/v solution of trifluoroacetic acid, acetonitrile for chromatography in ratio 1:100 (%v/v). The flow rate was set to 0.7 ml/min. Gradient program was incorporated with chromatography run time of 20 minutes with UV detection at 242 nm. During the lifecycle of the in-house method in the laboratories for finished products and long-term stability, issues with non-fulfilment of the criteria for System suitability test were observed. From the results obtained from monographic method it was claimed by the authors that with the newly optimized method, the problems with achieving System Suitability Test criteria have been overcome, a better chromatogram has been obtained and the duration time of one analysis has been significantly shortened. [46]

Prahlad V S R B M, Swetha V (2021) developed a method to estimate Teneligliptin using Gas Chromatography, Chromatographic separation in GC was performed using a DB-624 column (30 meters, 0.53 mm diameter, 3 μ m film thickness) with Dimethyl acetamide as the diluent. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas, flowing through the column at a pressure of 2.5 psi. The detector temperature was set at 250°C. Stressed samples were analyzed with a Flame Ionization Detector to identify Teneligliptin Hydrochloride Hydrate. [47]

Patil P M, Jain P S, Surana S J, Yeole S D (2017) developed a HPTLC method for estimation of Teneligliptin in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulation. HPTLC separation was achieved using aluminium plates pre-coated with silica gel 60F254 [20 cm X 10 cm with 0.2 mm thickness] and a mobile phase consisting of Methanol: Toluene: Triethylamine (1:3:1 v/v/v), optimized for detection at a wavelength of 245 nm. The retardation factor (R_f) value for Teneligliptin was 0.63. The accuracy for the commercially available formulation ranged from 98.31% to 100.51%. The percent relative standard deviation for both repeatability and intermediate precision studies was less than 2%. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 67.42 ng/band and 204.42 ng/band respectively. [48]

Sunitha PG, Karthikeyan R, Kumar R B, Muniyappan S (2017) had developed two colorimetric methods for the estimation of Teneligliptin in tablet dosage form. In the first method, the red coloured chromogen was formed by reaction of Teneligliptin with potassium thiocyanate in presence of ferric chloride which had absorption maxima at 554 nm. In the second method, Orange colored complex was formed by the reaction of Teneligliptin 2,2-bipyridal in the presence of ferric chloride which had absorption maxima at 421 nm. The linearity of the methods was observed in the concentration range of 0.1-0.6 μ g/ml ($R^2 = 0.9999$) for first method and 0.2-1.6 μ g/ml ($R^2 = 0.9999$) for the second method. The mean % assay was found as 100.01 % for first method and 99.99 % for the second method. [49]

Lodha S R, Patel K D, Patel S A, Patel S G et al (2016) developed a stability-indicating HPTLC method to estimate Teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate in tablet form. Chromatographic separation was carried out on aluminum plates pre-coated with silica gel 60 F254, using a mobile phase of butanol: water: glacial acetic acid (6:2:2 v/v/v) and scanned densitometrically at 245 nm. The R_f value for Teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate was 0.65. The solvent system effectively separated Teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate from its degradation products formed under acidic conditions. The method was validated according to ICH guideline Q2(R1). Linear regression analysis of calibration plots demonstrated a strong linear relationship with an R² value of 0.998 across a concentration range of 250-1250 ng/band for Teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate. The percent recovery of the drug ranged from 98.58% to 99.24%. The limit of detection and limit of quantitation were 60.50 ng/band and 183.36 ng/band, respectively. The method was applied to determine Teneligliptin hydrobromide hydrate in tablet dosage form, yielding an assay result of 98.34 \pm 0.31%. [50]

Baldut M, Bonafede S L, Petrone L, Simionato L D, Segall A I (2015) developed a new method for quantifying Rosuvastatin calcium using complexometric titration. This technique involves reacting Rosuvastatin calcium with a complexing agent, EDTA and measuring the endpoint to determine its concentration. The method was carefully developed and validated for accuracy, precision, and reliability. The assay results were found to be 98.5-99.7%. Statistical results showed that the method had a recovery range of 98.9% to 99.1% and a Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) of less than 2.0%, indicating both high accuracy and consistency. [51]

Raj HA, Rajput SJ, Dave JB, Patel CN (2009) had developed HPLC and HPTLC method to determine Rosuvastatin in presence of its degradation products in raw material. In HPLC method, separation was achieved using Phenomenex C18 column using acetonitrile: 0.5% formic acid (50:50 % v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min the detection was carried out at 248 nm. The retention time was found to be 6.74 min. Rosuvastatin showed linearity over concentration range of 5-300 µg/ml with a recovery in range of 99.51-100.66 %. % Assay was found to be in range of 100.18-100.45 %, LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.0905 µg/ml and 0.318 µg/ml respectively. For HPTLC method separation was carried out on silica gel 60F₂₅₄ using ethylacetate: toluene: acetonitrile: formic acid (6: 3.5: 0.5: 0.2 v/v/v/v) as mobile phase with UV detection of the separated bands carried out at 243 nm, this method showed a mean recovery in range of 99.77-101.94%. Rosuvastatin showed linearity over concentration range of 318-3816 ng/spot, LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.986 ng/spot and 2.682 ng/spot respectively, Mean % assay was found to be 102.93 %. [52]

Conclusion

This review article presents the physico-chemical properties of Rosuvastatin and Tenelegliptin. It compiles information on various analytical methods reported in the literature for the individual determination of Rosuvastatin and Tenelegliptin. The review highlights that a range of techniques, such as UV spectroscopy, HPTLC, HPLC, and GC, have been used for their estimation. However, RP-HPLC and UV spectrophotometric methods are the most reported. Most UV spectroscopic methods for both Rosuvastatin and Tenelegliptin utilize zero-order approaches. Notably, the literature reveals that no methods have been reported for the simultaneous estimation of Rosuvastatin and Tenelegliptin in a fixed-dose combination. Given that the CDSCO recently approved a fixed-dose combination (FDC) containing both drugs, this review aims to assist in the development of analytical methods for this novel combination.

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